

How Important is Spatial Invariance Symmetry to Quantum Mechanics?

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In physical problems there may exist various symmetries. A common one is spatial invariance or translational symmetry. In other words, one may have an interaction occur at x_1 or x_2 with exactly the same physical outcome. For example, if a photon bounces off a mirror, and this is the only reaction in the physical picture, it does not matter where the mirror is located in space. This might suggest that x does not appear in an equation describing a system with spatial invariance symmetry. This, however, may not always be the case because one may have $f(x_1-x_2)$, as in the case of the length of the sides of a right angle triangle. In the case of a photon reflecting from a mirror, the mirror may be at any x point, but one may think of the reflected photon as being a continuation of the original one in a space which ends at x , the mirror location. In such a case, it is as if there is no interaction. We argue, however, that such reasoning does not explicitly demonstrate spatial translational symmetry. We suggest that even in a reflection problem which seems to have a reflected solution with a probability of 1, $-p$ and $-v$ (velocity), spatial translational invariance must explicitly appear. This suggests that there is more to the problem than meets the eye and in fact, quantum mechanics shows that the photon has a phase linked to $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ appears if one takes a reflection equation: $AA/c = AA/c$ where AA is the incident and reflected flux. We argue that AA should really be A^*A , suggesting $A \rightarrow A \exp(i f(x))$. If one wishes to enforce continuity of $A \exp(i f(x))$ and its first derivative, then one has $A \exp(ipx)$. Thus, the quantum mechanical $\exp(ipx)$ appears from considering translational invariance symmetry even in a reflection problem.

We extend these ideas to a one dimensional reflection-refraction of photon (or the corresponding problem for a particle). The interface point along the y axis at $x=x_1$ (with an index of refraction n_1 for $x < x_1$ and n_2 for $x > x_1$) should have spatial invariance (i.e translational invariance of the interface point). This is a basic physical symmetry and there is no reason why this should not explicitly appear in equations solving this problem, we argue. The problem is that there does not seem to be any physically relevant reason for introducing x . One simply introduces probabilities to reflect and refract together with the notion of fluxes and speeds which may be linked to a conservation of photon number and energy. This conservation law, however, is not sufficient to solve the problem and we suggest that it is in fact, the absence of a translationally invariant x functions from such an equation which is the problem. In other words, one cannot ignore symmetry in a problem. It should manifest itself in the equations used to find the solution. We suggest that this has consequences, because x , which would normally have nothing to do with a one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem, must now appear in equations used to find the solution, such that it is invariant. We suggest that this leads to breaking an equation which does not display x into two which do such that these may be recombined to remove x , i.e. display translational invariance.

In other words, x must ultimately disappear, but it must be present at the beginning, otherwise basic physical information is being discarded. We suggest that these basic ideas of incorporating translational invariance into a problem which seems not to explicitly require the presence of x actually leads to the form $\exp(ipx)$ of a quantum free particle.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

A one dimensional reflection-refraction problem in which a photon travels to the right along the x axis and meets an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface along the y axis at x_1 involves probabilities to reflect and refract as well as fluxes, speeds and momenta. For a photon the relation $E=pc$ exists and one may suggest that E is conserved. In such a case, it is immediately clear that photon number and energy must be conserved, i.e. If A, B, C are the incident, reflected and refracted fluxes (written as value*value to indicate positivity), then conservation of photon number is given by:

$$A/c_1 = B/c_1 + C/c_2 \quad \text{where } c_1=c/n_1 \text{ and } c_2=c/n_2 \quad ((1))$$

No x value appears in ((1)), yet there is translational invariance symmetry in the problem. We ask: Is that relevant and if so why? For a photon reflecting off of a mirror, one may move the mirror to any point x and ignore x altogether, it seems. (Actually, quantum mechanically two photons reflecting from mirrors at different x points and meeting at some x to the left will be out of phase, so the x point is important, but in a subtle way.) In terms of probability, the incident photon reflects with a probability of 1 so it is as if space winds backwards and one has a kind of one dimensional problem. Thus, one does not really pay attention to the location of the mirror in a reflection problem. This we argue, however, is not really correct. Physically translational symmetry is important. We suggest that to be fully correct physically one should not “throw away” spatial invariance. If that is the case, how does one incorporate it into an equation which does not seem to depend on x?

Given that the probability to reflect is 1, one may write:

$$\text{Number of incident photons} = \text{number of reflected photons} \quad ((2))$$

Using A as photon flux, ((2)) becomes: $A/c = A/c$ ((3)) where A indicates positivity.

There is no x appearing in ((3)), but it is easy to mathematically introduce it in a manner that one has translational invariance by replacing A with $A \exp(i f(x))$. In such is the case, A becomes A^*A and any function f(x) suffices. Given the existence of a function of x, namely $A \exp(i f(x))$, one may consider issues of continuity of this function and its first derivative at the mirror, i.e. the x point associated with translational invariance. ((3)) is equivalent to two equations multiplied together: $A=A$ and $A/c=A/c$. Alternatively, one may use $A^*=A^*$ if one has complex results. If one wishes to have continuity of $A \exp(i f(x))$ and its first derivative at $x=x_1$, then $f(x)= x/c = px/E$ is a solution because $E=pc$. In fact, one does not have to use $\exp(i f(x))$, but could use base power(i f(x)). If one considers E to be a constant in the problem, then there is no reason to worry about E in px/E . One only needs x and p because x changes and p may change. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ seems to be fine as an explicit function which demonstrates the translational invariance of the mirror position. They may seem unnecessary in the mirror reflection problem as it is not needed to solve for the probability for reflection, this is a priori known to be 1. Nevertheless, we argue that translational invariance is a physical symmetry and should appear in the solution for this problem, but then ultimately disappear. In the case of the

length of a right triangle side, it appears explicitly in (x_1-x_2) which is manifestly translationally invariant. In the case of an equation with a quadratic form, i.e. AA , it may appear as a phase $\exp(if(x))$. If one tries to map a conservation equation containing no x value, one may try to break it into two equations, with one representing x continuity of $\exp(if(x))$ and the other, continuity of its first derivative. Combining the two equations using complex conjugates removes the presence of x . The two equations, however, show the existence of an $\exp(ipx)$ which is based on a physical invariance and so must be physical itself, we argue.

At first the above may seem to be belabouring the point, but we suggest that the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem is an example which more clearly illustrates the above ideas.

Given ((1)), there is no spatial invariance present, but there are AA terms which may be replaced with A^*A and A with $A\exp(if(x))$ in order to explicitly bring x into the problem. Given that x does not appear in A^*A , it seems one must break ((1)) into two equations so that x is explicitly present. This might seem like overkill in the strictly reflection problem, but here in ((1)) there are two unknowns B and C , given a known AA ie. incident flux. Breaking ((1)) into two equations allows one to solve for B and C in terms of A , but is breaking ((1)) simply a math trick?

We suggest that the underlying reason for creating two equations is to explicitly display translational invariance which is a physical symmetry in the problem and must appear. We thus suggest that symmetries in problems are critical to the full solution of the problem. In the case of sole reflection from a mirror, it is incomplete to state that the reflected photon only has a negative p , v and the same probability as the incident. There are x related issues present which are experimentally measurable.

For the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, one may write continuity of $\exp(if(x))$ and its first derivative. The first derivative term should yield $1/ci$ or E/ci or p , so we suggest that $f(x)$ must be px . Then:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=x_1 \quad ((4a))$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = Cp2 \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=x_1 \quad ((4b))$$

Thus, x appears explicitly in ((4a)) and ((4b)), but to demonstrate its invariance, it must disappear when one multiplies the complex conjugate of ((4a)) by ((4b)), which in fact happens due to the difference of squares form.

One may actually solve this problem without explicitly using the form $\exp(ipx)$, but using $x_1=0$, but this still begs the question: Why was ((1)) broken into two equations. We suggest that this occurred in order to explicitly introduce x due to the physical translational invariance symmetry.

Thus, we suggest that the $\exp(ipx)$ feature of quantum mechanics may be traced to spatial translational symmetry which may be easily overlooked.

Classical Particle

We note that the conservation equation ((1)) has the form of a pressure balance if $1/c_i$ is replaced with p_i and BB brought to the LHS. This same balance may be applied to a particle with rest mass which reflects/refracts from a constant V_1 potential - V_2 constant potential interface. Again, there is spatial invariance at the V_1 - V_2 interface point, so x must appear explicitly. Thus, the above ideas still hold. Note: E energy is the same for the reflected and refracted particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that symmetries in nature are very important and need to be manifest explicitly in equations describing physical behaviour. If translational symmetry is present in a problem, then x should appear manifestly, but the invariance must also be displayed. One way is to have $f(x_1-x_2)$, but in some problems, such as photon reflection or one-dimensional reflection-refraction, x does not seem to appear at all. One might argue that this shows the invariance, but we suggest one must have equations displaying x and that these then may lead to results in which x disappears. By having x dependent equations, one actually introduces new physics (i.e. a function of x which must have physical meaning as the symmetry is physical) and so may be measurable (in fact in the quantum case very much so). We suggest that forcing an x function into a reflection or one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, breaks an equation with no x into two containing $\exp(i f(x))$. If one insists on continuity of this function and its first derivative at an x junction (linked with spatial translational invariance), then $f(x)=px$. If a difference of squares appears or a sole $\exp(ipx)$ on one side of an equation, one may take the complex conjugate of one equation and multiply it by the first derivative equation to see that $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. explicit x dependence, disappears. Thus, stating that spatial invariance means that x must appear in some equation and then be shown to disappear (due to the invariance) leads to the $\exp(ipx)$ form of quantum mechanics, we argue.